

THE ROLE OF INDEPENDENT WORK OF STUDENTS IN INCREASING THEIR COGNITIVE ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. *The given article reveals a systematic approach to the organization of independent work of students. The concepts and essence of independence are analyzed and the importance of independent work in the educational activities of students is substantiated. The methods of activating students' independent work as a condition of their cognitive activity are described. Pedagogical conditions are proposed that facilitate the effective implementation of an individual approach to teaching students in higher education.*

Keywords: *higher school, independent activity, independent work, systematic approach, methodical readiness, pedagogical conditions, cognitive activity.*

It is important to suggest that independent work of students, developing their cognitive skills, forming independence in the process of studying at the university, is a fundamental criterion for the development of cognitive activity of future highly qualified personnel.

Besides that, it should be noted that the study of the role of independent work of students, taking into account the rich historical experience of pedagogical science, conceptual and terminological disclosure of the concept, allows us to identify their components, features of thinking skills, cognitive activity and creative abilities.

Thus, in our opinion, the systematizing factor is the students' awareness of the goals of training, active participation in the formation and setting of goals, ways to achieve them. It is essential here that an individual student acts as the object of training, and not a group or a stream of students.

Additionally, independent work involves maximum activity of students in assimilation of the material studied in the classroom, when working with a textbook and additional literature. It manifests itself in purposeful perception, active processing, consolidation, conscious desire to turn the assimilated knowledge into personal convictions (appropriation of them). It should be emphasized that independent work of students can be based on a conscious or intuitive basis. [5, 105] In this case, the starting point for the correct organization of independent work is an understanding of the purpose, tasks, forms and methods of work, conscious control over this process.

In the second, a vague, indistinct understanding prevails, a habit formed under the influence of mechanical repetitions, imitation. Activation of independent work of students is impossible without reliance on consciousness. Each student can form his own individual style in organizing independent work, when the individual and the generally accepted form a balanced unity. Formation of an individual style on a conscious basis is one of the most important tasks of the methodology of organizing independent work of a student, since mastering rational methods of independent work is the assimilation of the experience of other people, correlated with scientific data and enriched by the personal experience of each specific person. Of no small importance is the teacher's awareness of the level of development of students, the degree of their readiness to

study a specific discipline (their level of knowledge, skills, abilities). At the same time, it is necessary to instill in students the ability to think creatively, solve problems and make appropriate and productive decisions. They will be able to achieve these goals only if teachers are receptive to the deeper and more complex thinking of students and learn to stimulate it.

Definitely, an effective system for classifying such thinking was developed by Benjamin Samuel Bloom, who divided thinking into six levels of cognitive development. [1, 21]. The lowest stage in this classification is called "knowledge" and means the ability to reproduce various types of information (facts, rules, etc.), and nothing more. Then we move on to understanding, that is, the ability to show that we have truly learned what we have learned. The third stage is called application, that is, the ability to apply what we have learned to new examples and situations. A higher stage can only be reached by going through the previous one. Therefore, when we move on to analysis, synthesis and, finally, evaluation, we have already overcome all possible stages of the educational process, including the highest stage of cognition. Each subsequent level requires good assimilation of the previous one, but at the same time, it is impossible to draw a clear distinction between them, since many questions actualize several levels at once.

In all forms of training, it is necessary to carefully compose assignments in accordance with the educational goals.

In this regard, it is necessary to adjust the course work program, i.e. bring it to the level of complexity of the material that L. S. Vygotsky called the "zone of proximal development" [2, 398]. Consciousness of learning will also be ensured by:

1. Methodological meaningfulness and consistency of the presented material;
2. Sequence of presentation, taking into account not only the logic of science, but also the psychology of assimilation;
3. Dosage of the volume of independent work corresponding to the educational capabilities of students;
4. Involvement of students in the type of activity that should be formed in them in accordance with the characteristics and job description.

It is very important to professionally orient the studied disciplines (profiling) when forming a conscious attitude to academic work. These problems are not sufficiently developed from the point of view of their justification, since the higher education system must take into account the real patterns of graduates' mental activity, which is quite difficult to ensure, for example, in fundamental courses of natural sciences. However, a number of requirements can be formulated.

Firstly, the educational material of each discipline should be selected and presented in such a way as to ensure the achievement of the goals formulated in the qualification characteristics, and students clearly understand why they need this discipline.

Secondly, it is necessary to constantly work on the educational material, not only keeping in mind bringing its content in line with the current state of knowledge, but also taking care to increase the level of its awareness, methodology, and conduct training sessions so that specific actions of students serve as a means of developing generalized skills.

Thirdly, in the theoretical part of the discipline, a fundamental core containing stable, unchanging knowledge should be identified. It is necessary to identify and demonstrate more widely its connections with other disciplines: the formation in the minds of students of a scientific picture of the world and modern methodology should be the concern of all academic disciplines.

Fourthly, educational tasks in all general disciplines should be formed meaningfully, taking into account the specifics of the future specialty of students.

However, universities create voluminous methodological guidelines that sometimes make independent cognitive activity of students impossible, strictly regulating it. Both of these approaches in the organization independent work of students are different types of constructing an indicative basis for actions, and their combination in university practice should provide an optimal character.

From our point of view, the most acceptable organizational forms of independent work of students should be developed (and adapted for each university), i.e. an information database of all types and forms of independent work of students known to all teachers. It should be noted that the organization of independent work presupposes, first of all, the general organization of the daily routine, taking into account biorhythmology, the generally rhythmic work of students during the day, hygiene and the organization of mental work. [3, 156]

It is important to emphasize that when organizing an integrated system of independent work of students for the entire period of study at a university, it is necessary first of all to resolve the issue of its hierarchical levels, each of which should be associated with a certain degree of independence of students. The literature describes and practically applies various methods for activating students' independent work.

As a rule, they are aimed at maintaining interest in learning, developing the ability to work independently and encouraging systematic work. A significant portion of the methods are described below:

1. Teaching students' methods of independent work, including: communicating reflective knowledge necessary for self-analysis and self-assessment; communicating the estimated time in the guidelines for students' independent work or assignments, necessary for completing the assignment.

2. Convincingly demonstrating the need to master the proposed for students' upcoming professional and educational activities in the introductory sections of lectures, textbooks and guidelines.

3. Problem-based presentation of the material, reproducing typical methods of real reasoning used in science and technology.

4. Using operational formulations of laws and definitions in order to establish an unambiguous connection between theory and practice.

5. Using active learning methods (business games, analysis of specific situations, collective discussion of complex issues, critical analysis of concepts, discussions, etc.).

6. Developing and communicating to students structural and logical diagrams of the discipline, its section, topic, complex conclusion or proof; using drawings that objectify high-level abstractions.

7. At the initial stage of studying each new discipline for first- and second-year students, issuing methodological instructions of an algorithmic type, such instructions that describe the full sequence of actions.

8. Developing comprehensive teaching aids for independent work containing theoretical material intersecting with methodological instructions and tasks for independent work.

9. Individualization of homework and laboratory work. If the work is collective, then each student must be responsible for a certain, precisely specified section of the work.

10. During lectures in small streams (two to four groups), conducting short (approximately 10 minutes) tests: both before each lecture two or three questions on the material of the previous lecture; and at the end of each lecture it is necessary to formulate several questions on the material of the current lecture; the same homework assignment due at the next lecture.

11. Involve the most successful students in holding consultations with those who are experiencing difficulties. Work with student consultants.

12. Develop a methodology for conducting group classes. Their advantages: competitiveness; students' correct assessment of their successes by comparing them with the successes of their peers; developing the ability to work in a group.

Consequently, the process of assimilating and merging the products of someone else's experience with one's own is the psychological basis for independent work, while one's own experience is understood during independent processing of information. [4, 289].

At the same time, independently acquired knowledge is in turn a kind of personal experience, since in order to assimilate knowledge, it must be acquired.

In conclusion, it should be suggested that the analysis of the organization of independent work of students allows us to make a certain conclusion: independent work of students is one of the main components of professional training of students, and this role logically follows from the entire system of higher and secondary - special education, aimed at achieving maximum practical efficiency, satisfying the immediate interests of society.

REFERENCES

1. Bloom, B. (1994). Taxonomy of educational goals: Classification of educational goals: Handbook I, cognitive area. Longman
2. Vygotsky L. S. Collected Works. - Moscow: Pedagogy, 1982. - Vol. 2. - P. 398.
3. Efimenko K. R. Mental work - the basis for the education of the younger generation. - Moscow: Medicine, 2012. - P. 156.
4. Petrovsky A. V., Yaroshevsky M. G. Psychology. – Moscow: Academy, 2000. – P. 289.
5. Independent work and academic success. / Research theory, practice. / Materials of the fifth international scientific and practical conference University education: from effective teaching to effective learning, / Minsk, March 29-30, 2005. – P. 105.